

Nanoparticle stability from the nano to the meso interval

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Nanoparticles are the cornerstone of nanotechnology. Its crystal structure and its relation to shape is still an open problem despite a lot of advances in the field. The classical theory of nanoparticle stability predicts that for sizes $<1.5 - 2$ nm the icosahedral structure should be the most stable, then
10 between around $2 - 5$ nm, the decahedral shape should be the most stable. Beyond that, face centered cubic (FCC) structures will be the predominant phase. However, in the experimental side, icosahedral (I_h) and decahedral (D_h) particles can be observed much beyond the 5 nm limit. In fact, it is possible to find I_h and D_h particles even in the mesoscopic range. Conversely, it is possible to find FCC particles with a size < 1.5 nm. In this paper we review a number of
15 mechanisms that allow the stabilization of the nanoparticles that have been proposed in the literature. Some of the mechanisms are very interrelated and it becomes difficult to distinguish between them.

Introduction

Crystals have attracted the attention of mankind since
20 prehistoric times. Driven by the interest in ornaments, technology for cutting crystals was developed to the point of making it an art form. However, it was not until much later in the human history when a scientific approach was taken into crystals; it probably occurred for the first time in 1669
25 when Steno observed quartz crystals and discovered that the angle between different faces was constant and independent of the size¹⁻³. In 1784 Haüy proposed the law of constant interfacial angles. So it is quite straightforward to assume that from the early days in crystallography shape was the central
30 issue^[2-3]. First studies in this field were based on measuring the angles between faces and the symmetry relations on the crystals. Structure was obtained from the shape of the crystal since many polyhedral forms were observed such as cubes, octahedra, tetrahedra and others, therefore Geometry became
35 a major tool in describing crystals⁴, a good example of this is the Euler relationship which allowed the calculation of the number of faces (F) on a polyhedron which is connected with the number of corners (C) and edges (E) by:

$$40 \quad E = F + C - 2 \quad (1)$$

Making the study of crystals an exact science even before the discovery of the atom. The French Physicist Auguste Bravais⁵ introduced the concept of lattice which implies that crystals
45 are formed as a result of a periodic array of motifs. Translated into atomic view, motifs are atoms and facets are now lattice planes, which correspond to high density planes of lattice atoms (Bravais Law).

The crystal structure can be explained in terms of imaginary
50 planes where atoms would lie. These planes are the so called lattice planes, which extend throughout the entire crystal structure intersecting the unit cells at specific points and

which are generally described by Miller indices denoted as (h, k, l). The Miller indices, which describe lattice planes, tend to
55 have small values therefore shapes of crystals will be formed by facets with low index Miller indices. Facets are also found in natural. Figure 1 shows some examples of minerals of calcite and sodium chlorate, proving that equilibrium in the natural crystals sometimes implies faceting.

60 Taking a more mathematical approach a crystal lattice should have symmetry axis of order n. If a lattice vector T (joining two points) is rotated by an angle $\frac{2\pi}{n}$ the vector -T is also a lattice vector in general a rotation by $\frac{2\pi}{n}$ will also produce lattice vectors T' or T'' (Fig. 2) whose difference is also a
65 lattice vector.

From figure 2 we have that

$$T' - T'' = mT$$

Where m is an integer, written in scalar form we obtain that:

$$70 \quad 2 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{n}\right) = m \quad (2)$$

$$m = \text{integer.}$$

This equation is only valid for $m = 1, 2, 3, 4, 6$, where the space would be filled by rectangles, triangles, squares and
75 hexagons⁶. In other words, we can form a lattice (filling the space) with objects with symmetries other than 5. This leads into a very interesting fact; we cannot fill the space with a pentagon (Fig. 3a). No matter how we pack them we will leave gaps behind⁷. If we now consider a regular tetrahedron
80 and we try to produce a decahedron we have no choice other than leaving a gap (Fig. 3b), that somehow has to be closed to form decahedral particles.

If we go back to the regular platonic solids, (Table 1), we should expect that crystals should have shapes such as cubes,
85 tetrahedra or octahedra but no shapes such as the dodecahedron or the icosahedrons which have five fold symmetry axis. However, against what it is expected these shapes are commonly observed in materials synthesized in the

nano and in the microscopic size range. Although macroscopic icosahedral shaped crystals are not naturally produced, fivefold nanoparticles have been found in meteorites⁸ and minerals⁹⁻¹³. The reader is referred to the review of Hofmeister¹⁴ for further insight on this topic.

Solid	Group
cube	O _h
dodecahedron	I _h
icosahedron	I _h
octahedron	O _h
tetrahedron	T _d

Table 1. List of platonic solids

Shapes of nanocrystals

As discussed in the previous section, fivefold symmetry is not allowed in bulk crystals, however, when we observe them in the nano and mesoscopic range we can see that decahedral and icosahedral shapes can be produced in the whole size range as shown in Figure 4, proving that fivefold structures can be produced from a few nm to thousands of nm.

In the case of the decahedra (as shown in figure 4b and 4c), when they are elongated, even very large nanowires^{15, 16} (Figure 5) can be produced with a fivefold symmetry axis. The question that comes in mind is why this is produced?

The “impossible” formation of particles with fivefold symmetry axis was a topic seriously debated in the sixties and seventies¹⁷⁻²⁵. One point of view assumed that a star disclination (Figure 6) was responsible of closing the gap and it corresponded to inhomogeneous strain meanwhile; the other view, described the phenomenon by assuming a distortion that would lead into a rhombohedral lattice^{21, 26} for the icosahedron and a body centered orthorhombic for the decahedron^{17, 21, 27, 28}. This point was addressed more recently by Johnson et al.²⁹, which have found that both kinds of mechanisms might be involved in the stabilization of materials presenting fivefold symmetry axis.

The main question that arises in order to understand the formation of these anomalous shaped nanocrystals is to consider if the D_h and I_h shapes are equilibrium shapes or are the result of the growth kinetics³⁰. An experiment to address this problem is shown in figure 7. A decahedral particle (Figure 7a), which was synthesized by using the standard evaporation method, was heated inside the electron microscope by irradiation with the electron beam. The temperature was estimated to be a 500°C during 3 min. The resulting structure (Figure 7b) was still a decahedron but the facets are curved and grooves are developed resembling to the Wulff polyhedron, which will be the expected to be an equilibrium structure^{31, 32}.

In a similar way an icosahedral crystal was heated at the same temperature and the result was a dome shaped crystal shown in Figure 8. Therefore, we should infer that nanoparticles with a fivefold axis of symmetry are not equilibrium structures.

The relevant point to understand is how these structures are produced during the growth of the nanoparticle³³ and how they are stabilized in order to form large nanoparticles which can reach several micrometers. In this work, we point out four main mechanisms that would stabilize the fivefold nanoparticles and that could lead into several micrometers sized decahedra or icosahedra.

Mechanism to stabilize fivefold nanoparticles

- Internal Strain.
- Introduction of planar defects (Twins, stacking faults).
- The introduction of steps, and kinks on the surface.
- External modification of shape by facet truncation.
- Other Mechanisms

In the following sections the different mechanisms will be discussed in detail.

Internal strain in nanoparticles

Nowadays, with the implementation of the aberration corrected transmission electron microscopy the internal strain produced in these structures³⁴⁻³⁷ can be studied in very high detail in both, TEM and STEM, modes³⁸⁻⁴⁰, opening up a whole new understanding at atomic level⁴¹⁻⁴⁶. An example of this work has been reported by Johnson *et al.*²⁹, who observed decahedral nanoparticles using Cs corrected TEM. They found that, at least partially declinations relieve the strain. However, the complete mechanism appear more complex involving a significant shear strain which suggests that a combination of the proposed models of Yacaman *et al.*^{18, 19} and Marks^{20, 47} must play a significant role on the stabilization of these materials. In the coming years it is expected that many results from aberration corrected STEM-TEM will provide more extensive information on the strain mechanism. The main reason is that in STEM images particularly on the high angle annular dark field mode (HAADF) the intensity is $\sim Z^2$ (Z = atomic number) and no dynamical effects contribute to the image. Therefore, variations in atomic distances observed on an image should be very close to the real value and therefore strain can be analyzed more accurately.

Another technique, which has become very important in order to incorporate additional information, is weak beam dark field electron microscopy (WBDF). In this method a dark field image is obtained from a diffraction spot which is far from the Bragg condition. Very closely space thickness fringes are produced. By the use of WBDF^{38, 39, 48} it is possible to plot strains as shown in figure 9. This image was created using the (200) diffraction spot and tilted 2° away from the Bragg condition. An appealing image is produced where thickness lines produced by variations on thickness cross a region of high strain (see arrow). Therefore, it is possible to conclude that the shifting observed on the fringes is attributed to the strain on the nanoparticles. By measuring that shifting the strain can be estimated.

Planar defects on fivefold nanoparticles

The fact that particles as decahedra or icosahedra are composed by tetrahedral units linked by faces leads into the formation of defects, such as stacking faults or secondary twin

boundaries, which releases the stress by accommodating it contributing into the stabilization of the particles as seen in figure 10. As mentioned above WBDF technique has been proved to be a good method to observe defects on metal nanoparticles as faces linked by defects may appear with different contrast (figure 10b and 10c)⁴⁸. These defects are formed as a result of a minimization of the twin boundary energy⁴⁹, forming, in some cases, simple twin planes where two adjacent faces are perfect mirror planes or in other cases, by the formation of more complex twin boundaries also involving additional stacking faults. Figure 10c and 10d presents a decahedral gold nanoparticle recorded along [110] orientation exhibiting fivefold symmetry, where the twin boundaries involve more than a single layer of atoms.

Defects can also induce transformations of one structure into another. Koga *et al.*⁵⁰ have shown that in I_h particle can transform into a D_h particle without diffusion when a cooperative slip dislocation of the (111) planes occurred.

In order to explain defects on icosahedral nanoparticles this can be considered as two pentagonal bipyramids joined with a common fivefold axis, to which ten additional tetrahedral units are added to complete the I_h structure. These tetrahedra become slightly distorted fcc tetrahedral units when each (111) face in the ten tetrahedra slips into the underlying (111) plane with a Burgers vector $b = a/6 \langle 112 \rangle$. The collective deformation of the ten tetrahedra leaves a D_h structure, being a diffusionless transformation. Another case has been described by Ascencio *et al.*⁵¹ who have reported the truncated icosahedral shape. This is produced by joining two decahedral structures and rotating them by 36° around the axis. This structure is formed by (111) like facets with triangular shape and (100) like trapezoid facets. This structure was also found by Montejano *et al.*⁵², who termed it “decmon” structure, which is shown in Figure 11. Rossi and Ferrando⁵³ have also shown how polydecahedral nanoparticles can be produced including the Koga bydecahedral structure⁵⁴. So, it is possible to conclude that planar defects on nanoparticles may help to stabilize a fivefold and more complex structures.

Steps and kinks

In order to introduce the topic we should discuss the standard model of a surface FK-L as terrace – KINK- Ledge which was introduced in the 20’s by Kossel⁵⁵ and has been a corner stone in understanding the growth of crystals. A schematic of this model is shown in figure 12 and it can be described as a surface may contain flat terraces (A) step (or ledges) (B) and KINKS (C).

Steps edges formed on crystals nanoparticles can play a crucial role in a variety of processes such as thermal roughening or faceting influencing the kinetics during crystal growth and as consequence the final morphology. These defects not only have a strong influence on the particle growth but also on the reactivity and much of the surface chemistry carried out of nanomaterials are believed to be related to their defects⁵⁶⁻⁶³. The stepped faces formed on the solids commonly present high miller indices. In order to explain such an extraordinary high values it is necessary to introduce long range interactions between the atoms therefore, facets are

stabilized when the range of interaction energy is increased to further neighbor pairs until corrugated faces appear (stepped or “vicinal” surfaces)⁶⁴. High Miller indices facets commonly can be decomposed into lower indices. An example of the (199) vicinal surface will become $\rightarrow 4(100) \times (111)$ ⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷. This surface will make an angle of 8.43° with respect to $\langle 100 \rangle$, as shown in figure 13.

This rough surface can be smooth by increasing the temperature. Corners and edges can become rounded as facets shrink finally disappearing over the “roughening transition temperature”⁶⁸, T_R , creating a smooth rounded surface when $T > T_R$.

A good example for the stabilization of fivefold twined nanomaterials where high Miller indices are present in the structure have been described for Pt nanorods^{69, 70}. In this material $\{hk0\}$ high-index facets are formed in the central part which ends in decagonal pyramids exhibiting the fivefold symmetry.

In addition, surfaces will have adatoms, island vacancies and adatoms at a step to complete the structure.

If we want to calculate the surface free energy of a particle or crystal we should assume that for large enough particles (50 Å) steps, ledges, vacancies and kinks will be present. The surface free energy will be function of the temperature and of the density of steps ω . So we can write⁷¹

$$E_s(TP) = E_0(T) + E_1(T)\omega + E_3(T)\omega^3 \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Where E_0 will be the surface energy of a flat terrace, $E_1(T)$ the surface energy of an isolated step and $E_3(T)$ is the surface energy due to step interaction. The interaction is of two types: repulsive and attractive. In the former case the repulsive force will stabilize the vicinal surfaces. An attractive force will result in a smoothing of the vicinal surfaces. The step-step force will have two components: one elastic and one entropic in nature⁷². There are several ways to calculate the shape of particles⁷³ from the Wulff construction to the Ising model. In all cases the energy will be minimized to reach equilibrium.

We can ask now: Do the nanoparticles have steps and kinks? If we consider particles in the size range of $>50\text{\AA}$, the answer is yes. Ferrer *et al.*⁷⁴ have demonstrated that in the case of Au/Pd, atomic level HAADF images clearly revealed the steps and kinks on the surface. Figure 14 shows the image and the calculated structure of an Au/Pd nanoparticle. This calculation was made by comparing the measured intensities with image calculations. The only way that a matching can be found is by assuming a kinked and stepped surface on the particle.

It is now clear that for particles >50 nm the steps become dominant. An example of a star shaped particle can be seen in Figure 15, where steps on the surface are clearly visible.

Truncations, wedges and notches

A very general phenomenon observed in nanoparticles is the fact that truncations, wedges and notches are often observed in nanoparticles. Probably the most well known example is the Marks decahedron⁷⁵, which shows extra (111) facets in the form of notches. Recently, a truncation on the icosahedral structure⁷⁶ has been proposed by Chui *et al.*^{77, 78}. These are

only two cases of a more general trend. As particles grow larger there is a clear tendency to develop additional (111) facets. That results in the formation of higher polyhedral, shown in figure 16. The fact that part of the image is in focus where other portion is out of focus shows a height difference larger than the depth of focus of the TEM. The height was estimated by defocusing experiments in around 5-6 interatomic spacings. Of course, faceting will also be connected with kinks of the kind discussed in the previous section. At first glance it will appear that truncations are just the result of growth kinetics. To illustrate this point we consider a square FCC crystal growing on a supersaturated solution. If the velocity of growth in the (100) direction is larger than the velocity along (110) direction and fills the condition $v_{100} = \sqrt{2} v_{110}$ then the crystal will retain a square shape (Figure 17a). However, if for some reason $v_{110} > v_{(100)}$ then a (110) truncation will be produced (Figure 17b). Another example has been described by Elechiguerra *et al.*⁷⁹. In this case twins in an initially hexagonal particle introduced facets with different growth speed and the particle became a triangular particle. Growth speed might be altered by surface phenomena such as impurity adsorption or surface reconstruction. However, it can be shown that truncation can also be the result of thermodynamical equilibrium. It appears that as the nanoparticle size increases the truncation of facets will be more common. Figure 17 shows truncated nanoparticles which are commonly observed during the nanocrystal synthesis. Many of them are quite stable even after annealing.

30 Other mechanisms

Other relaxation mechanisms that involve the stabilization of nanoparticles with fivefold symmetry are related to the fivefold axis movement or splitting³⁶. The most important cases are:

- 35 1 Displacement of the fivefold axis which reduces the elastic energy (Figure 18a).
- 2 Splitting of the fivefold axis (Figure 18b). In this case a disclination can split in two or more partial disclinations having the same Frank vector⁸⁰.
- 40 Some other relaxation mechanisms might also be possible that will not be considered in the present paper.

Conclusions

In this review we have shown the importance of different aspects of the structure of nanoparticles which led to the stabilization of fivefold and other shapes not seen on bulk crystals. This is part of the unique properties of such materials at the nanoscale level. It is logical to assume that most of these shapes are kinetically produced and therefore do not correspond to equilibrium shapes. However, fivefold structures remain stable for sizes up to 500 nm and only by annealing the structure could produce an equilibrium shape. In addition, vicinal surfaces are present in nanoparticles >50 nm, which would lead into very high Miller index, that however, break down into low index facets and ledges. The result is that particles will have a structure with kinks, vacancies and adsorbed atoms, which can contribute to improve catalytic

properties. It is clear that the development of ultra high resolution TEM, STEM and SEM has contributed to advance the understanding of nanoparticle structure.

60 We have shown in this review that the structure of nanoparticles can be stabilized by several mechanisms such as strain, planar defects, kinks and steps among others. One of several of those mechanisms can operate in any given situation.

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Notes and references

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- [‡] Footnotes should appear here. These might include comments relevant to but not central to the matter under discussion, limited experimental and spectral data, and crystallographic data.
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Figure 1 Schematic representation, showing the crystal faces of a) Calcite (trigonal) and b) Sodium chlorate (regular).

Figure 2 Lattice points in a plane normal to the symmetry axis n passing through O .

Figure 3 a) Regular pentagons cannot fill planar space. b) For perfect f.c.c. tetrahedral subunits, the angle between adjacent $\{111\}$ faces, illustrated here in the $[110]$ projection, is 70.53° , which results in a 7.35° solid-angle deficiency. As a result of this deficiency, real nanoparticles must contain defects or be intrinsically strained.

Figure 4 Electron microscopy images of a) icosahedron of $\sim 80\text{nm}$, b) icosahedron of about 7nm . c) decahedron of $\sim 300\text{nm}$ and d) decahedron of few micrometers.

Figure 5 a) SEM image of a gold nanowire presenting fivefold symmetry axis. b) Schematic representation of the nanowire.

Figure 6 Partial disclinations in fcc crystals. They are edges lines of twin boundaries and pass through the point A. a) The $70^{\circ}32'$ partial disclination. b) The $7^{\circ}20'$ ($=360^{\circ}-5 \times 70^{\circ}32'$) partial disclination (star disclination) that borders five twin boundaries.

Figure 7 HRTEM images of a) Synthesized decahedral particle. b) Heated decahedral particle.

Figure 8 HRTEM images of a) icosahedral nanoparticle and b) the same particle which has been heated inside TEM.

Figure 9 WBDF TEM image of a gold nanoparticle, where contour lines represent the thickness are observed.

Figure 10 a) TEM image of a star shaped gold nanoparticle. b) WBDF TEM image of a) tilted 9 degrees, where the defects in the crystal are highlighted by the different contrast observed. c) TEM image of a rounded decahedral gold nanoparticle with very wide stacking faults. d) WBDF TEM image of c).

Figure 11 Schematic representation of the 'decmon' decahedron.

Figure 12 Schematic illustration of a vicinal surface with one-atom layer high steps, kinks in steps, adatoms on terraces and at steps, vacancies and islands formed by a group of adatoms.

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Figure 13 Ball model of the (1 1 9) surface of an fcc-crystal. The surface consists of 4.5 atom wide terraces, separated by monatomic step along a $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction.

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Figure 14 a) Aberration corrected STEM image of an Au/Pd nanoparticle, the interface is marked by a white square. b) calculated model for the Au/Pd nanoparticle.

Figure 15 High resolution SEM image of a hexagonal shaped gold nanoparticles presenting steps on the surface. b) High resolution TEM image of a gold nanoparticle where linear defects are observed.

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Figure 16 HRTEM of image of different polyhedral metal nanoparticles.

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Figure 17 Schematic representation of crystal growing at different velocities.

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Figure 18 Different ways of elastic energy relaxation in pentagonal particles. a) Shifting of the pentagonal axis and b) Decomposing the disclination into two others.

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